

GBCC

NRCC

NWCC

ONCC

OSCC

RMCC

SWCC

GBCC

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

NRCC

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

NWCC

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

ONCC

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

OSCC

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

RMCC

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

SWCC

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

